

Development of Scale Model Graphite/ Epoxy Retaining Rings for Generator Applications: An Overview

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ABSTRACT

A multidisciplinary EPRI sponsored program (RP1474-1) to design, manufacture, non-destructively inspect and spin test two 2/3 scale (27 in. I.D., 2.15 in. thick) graphite/epoxy composite retaining rings has been completed. To support ring design, considerable testing including determination of conventional physical properties, notched specimen properties, fatigue characteristics and biaxial loading of scale model cylinders was conducted.

At an operating temperature of 80°C both retaining rings withstood 3,000 cycles between 2,100 and 6,650 rpm with little or no growth in flaw size detectable by ultrasonic C-scan. A subsequent spin test of one ring at 7,870 rpm, which represents 2.8 times normal operating stress, was also successful. Prior to evaluation tests in an actual generator, both ring attachment and electrical flow distribution problems must be solved.

INTRODUCTION

Copper conductors in the rotor of turbine generators extend from the slots beyond the main rotor body where they are interconnected. During rotor rotation the coils are restrained and kept from moving in a radial direction by retaining rings which are shrunk onto the rotor ends. These non-magnetic rings weighing 4-5,000 lbs are manufactured from cold worked 18 Mn-5 Cr austenitic steel and have a tensile yield strength of $\sim 180,000$ psi.

At least three problems have been identified with currently used retaining ring materials (1). These are (1) 43-46 in. diameter rings are at the size limit for existing alloys, due to yield strength limitation, (2) existing alloys are subject to stress corrosion cracking, and (3) retaining rings are produced only by suppliers in Germany, France and Japan, and domestic (U.S.) suppliers do not exist for producing even the smaller metallic rings.

With these limitations in mind it was proposed to investigate the utility of graphite/epoxy composite retaining rings. Non-metallic composite rings offer numerous advantages to the electrical industry, chiefly with regard to maximum size potential and domestic supply sources. Size restraints on current 43 in. diameter steel alloy rings are related to the strength/density ratio, and

graphite/epoxy composites offer significant theoretical advantage due to their lower density, which is $\sim 1/5$ that of steel.

The objective of this paper is to present an overview of a two and one-half year EPRI sponsored program (RP1474-1) to design, develop and test scale model graphite/epoxy retaining rings. Data presented should serve as a platform from which future developments in the area of composite retaining rings can continue.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material Selection

Resin. Based on a knowledge of the properties of available filament winding resins, three candidates were identified as offering significant potential for the retaining ring application. These are listed in Table I along with design baseline data used in the finite element analysis to analyze and develop ring construction.

TABLE I - RESIN PROPERTY COMPARISONS

Resin System	Young's Modulus (psi x 10 ⁶)		Tensile Strength (psi x 10 ³)		% Elongation	
	25°C	120°C	25°C	120°C	25°C	100°C
	Design Analysis	0.470-0.500	--	10	--	2.5-4.5
Hercules 3501-6	0.550-0.640	0.540-0.600	7-9	7-8	1.5-2.0	3.0-3.5
Ciba XU235/XU205	0.510-0.600	0.410-0.500	8-11	5-7	2.5-3.0	3.5-4.0
DER330/Tonox LC	0.450-0.500	0.225-0.300	10-12	4-6	4.0-4.5	5.5-6.0

In addition to these resins, two graphite fibers - Hercules AS4/3K and Thornel 300/3K were selected as candidate reinforcements. Properties for these materials are given in Table II.

TABLE II - HERCULES AS4/3K AND THORNEL 300/3K PROPERTIES

Property	Value (U.S. Units)	Value (S.I. Units)
Tensile Strength	lb/in. ² x 10 ³	GPa
Tensile Modulus	lb/in. ² x 10 ⁶	GPa
Density	lb/in. ³	Mg/m ³
Filament Diameter	μ	μ M
Elongation at Break	%	%
Elastic Recovery	%	%
Carbon Assay	%	%
Surface Area	m ² /g	m ² /g
Thermal Conductivity	BTU/ft/hr(ft ²)(°F)	W/mK
Electrical Resistivity	ohm-cm x 10 ⁻⁴	ohm-cm
Longitudinal CTE at 70°F (21°C)	PPM/°F	PPM/K
Specific Heat at 70°F (21°C)	BTU/lb °F	J/kgK

Utilizing these matrix and fiber properties summarized below, a finite element analysis was conducted to predict stresses in retaining rings of various composite constructions.

Matrix Properties	Fiber Properties (AS Graphite)
E = 5.0 x 10 ⁵ psi	E = 34.0 x 10 ⁶ psi
ν = 0.40	ν = 0.25
ρ = 0.0460 lb/in. ³	ρ = 0.0655 lb/in. ³
α = 25.0 x 10 ⁻⁶ in./in.-°F	α = -0.20 x 10 ⁻⁶ in./in.-°F

where E = Young's modulus
 ν = Poissons' ratio
 ρ = density
 and α = coefficient of thermal expansion.

The output of this study led to an optimized construction of Hercules AS-4 fiber and Hercules 3501-6 resin with a fiber volume of ~60%. Construction identified was 410 plies with 86% hoop and 14% $\pm 45^\circ$ as shown below.

$$[90_4/\pm 45_2/90_{12}/\pm 45_2/90_{12} + 45 (45/90_{12}/\pm 45/90_{12}/-45)_6]_s.$$

Laminate Fabrication Procedures

Based on the design optimization work referenced in the preceding section, composite plate specimens of the desired construction up to 2.15 ins. thick were procured from Hercules, Inc. and inspected by ultrasonic C-scan prior to sectioning for test specimens. Then the material property tests listed below were conducted to support the design effort.

- o Conventional Design Properties (Tensile, Flexural, Modulus, Compression, etc.)
- o Notched Specimen Tests
 - Fracture Toughness (K_{IC})
 - Fatigue Crack Growth Rate (da/dn vs. ΔK)
 - Subcritical Crack Growth Rate (K_{ISCC})
- o Fatigue Testing (S-N Curve)
- o Biaxial Cylinder Loading

These experimental results will be detailed in subsequent reports to the Electric Power Research Institute and other publications that are in process or planned.

Retaining Ring Fabrication

Coincident with material property testing, two retaining rings were procured from Hercules, Inc. Although filament winding was considered initially to be the production method of choice, a new technique, bias ply winding, was used to construct the retaining rings. This decision was reached after a comparison of physical properties measured on cylinders made by the bias ply and filament winding techniques, as shown in Table III. These data demonstrate the

TABLE III - THICK WALL MECHANICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTY DATA

Composite System	Tensile Strength (psi x 10 ³)	Interlaminar Shear Strength (psi x 10 ³)	Calculated Young's Modulus (psi x 10 ⁶)	Void Content (%)	Fiber Content (%)
Bias Ply Technique					
AS4/3501-6	108	13	18.35	0.1	61.69
Filament Wound					
AS4/DER330/Tonox LC	104	7	--	6.23	58.38
Filament Wound					
AS4/XU235/UX205	105	6.5	--	6.09	58.59

superiority of the bias ply technique in reducing void content and producing a product with superior interlaminar shear characteristics, both of which are important to retaining ring integrity. The bias ply winding technique may be thought of as being related to convolute winding of tubes using a resin treated web of material. A schematic of the process is shown in Fig. 1. From a bias ply wound composite cylinder of nominal 48 in. length, two retaining rings, each 15.7 in. long with an I.D. of 27.5 in. and a wall thickness of 2.15 in., were machined. A typical ring weighing ~180 lbs is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 - Bias ply winding process

Fig. 2 - Graphite/epoxy retaining ring fabricated by Hercules, Inc.

An existing spin test facility was modified to accommodate the composite rings. This required manufacturing a flexible steel shaft, a high strength steel disk, a spinning cylinder loaded with dummy weights (to centrifugally load the cylinder during spin testing) and assembling these components. A schematic of the test facility is shown in Fig. 3. The rings were spin tested at 80°C

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Fig. 3—High-Speed test machine

according to the following sequence:

Ring 1

- a) Non-destructive Inspection
- b) 1,000 cycles between 2,100 and 6,650 rpm (20% overspeed)
- c) Non-destructive Inspection
- d) 2,000 additional cycles between 2,100 and 6,650 rpm for a total of 3,000 cycles
- e) Non-destructive Inspection

Ring 2

- a) Non-destructive Inspection
- b) 50 cycles between 2,100 and 6,650 rpm (20% overspeed)
- c) Non-destructive Inspection
- d) 2,950 additional cycles between 2,100 and 6,650 rpm for a total of 3,000 cycles
- e) Non-destructive Inspection

Both rings withstood these tests with no noticeable change in external appearance and no significant change in ultrasonic C-scan response.

Subsequent to conducting these cycling tests (which were designed to impose simulated cyclic loads expected in a normal 40 year operating life) ring 2 was spin tested at 7,870 rpm for ~5 mins. In this test the dummy weights used to centrifugally load the composite ring and simulate centrifugal loading by coils in the rotor were increased. With the combination of increased load and higher speed, an operating stress computed to be 2.8 times nominal was imposed. The ring withstood this high speed test with essentially no change in the ultrasonic C-scan response.

Ring Attachment and Sequence Current Distribution

Two material properties of the graphite composite present the generator designer with unique challenges. First, the electrical resistance is very high which means an additional "shorting ring" will be required to provide the end connection for the damper circuit. Second, the coefficient of thermal expansion is near zero, which means the usual method of heating the retaining ring to shrink fit it on the rotor will not be possible.

The designer faces a dilemma while attempting to design the graphite/epoxy composite retaining ring. In one case he cannot use the normal graphite/epoxy composite techniques of attachment while in the other case he cannot use the normal interference fit and keying arrangement. The normal composite attachment method is to use a reinforced bolted joint. In the retaining ring case the reinforcement may actually decrease the joint strength due to the resulting increase in centrifugal force. Also, the stress concentration from the bolt holes may be intolerable in an already highly stressed component. The other composite joint technique - using bonded joints - is of limited utility because of high "peel loads" and cleavage loads that exist at the interface between the rotor and retaining ring. The peel loads occur at standstill due to the retaining ring bending deflections and the cleavage loads occur during operation when the coils expand axially. Others (3) have tried hydraulic press fits; however, they have had limited success in demonstrating feasibility.

The Design Matrix Tool was used to choose the most promising alternative from among 12 different attachment concepts and six different damper connection systems. There are many (21 were identified) requirements which a retaining ring must meet; some critical ones are listed below:

Several key areas must continually be considered while evaluating the attachment schemes. The key area is the support of the copper coils as they exit the rotor body. The difficulty is caused by a different spring constant for the rotor body as compared to the retaining ring. Since limits are presently being approached for present ring designs, the graphite composite retaining ring design must be as good as or better than the steel retaining ring design.

Another key concern is rotor vibration. If the retaining ring continually shifts when coming up to speed or during field excitation, then it may become impossible to balance the rotor. This problem is minimized by:

- 1) "rigid" connection between the retaining ring and rotor,
- 2) balanced friction forces around the circumference between retaining ring and coils,
- 3) balanced temperatures around the circumference.

To prevent torsional slipping, the interference fit pressure during a fault must be greater than or equal to 2,000 psi (assumes a contact area of 425 in.² acting on a 20 in. radius with a coefficient of friction of 0.16).

Slot cell insulation wear occurs during rotation whenever the retaining ring compresses the slot cell against the slot bottom. For long rotors considerable sliding can occur once every revolution due to rotor static sag. This problem only occurs during turning gear operation since the slot cell lifts off the slot bottom during normal operation.

The main conclusions of ring attachment and current distribution are presented as follows.

The fiber composite retaining ring should not present major electrical problems in the operation of the generator. If properly implemented, the total electrical losses should be reduced. The penetration of the magnetic field flux into the rotor field winding has turned out not to be a problem. However, an additional peripheral damper circuit will be required near the end of the rotor

to carry the asynchronous rotor damper currents. From an electrical point of view an aluminum or copper "ring" with a cross-section of 4 ins. by 3/4 in. should be sufficient to carry these currents.

The main result from the finite element analysis on the retaining ring and copper end turn beam models is that a very stiff connection between the retaining ring and rotor will be required. This ruled out most attachment alternatives except for the following:

- o A combination hydraulic press fit with bonded joint concept which is similar to conventional retaining rings except that it has a tapered fit and provisions for pumping epoxy into the interface between the retaining ring and rotor.
- o An active damper ring concept which uses a high strength, low resistance, full length, conducting ring to carry damper currents and to carry axial and bending loads. The graphite ring is on the outside of this ring and only serves to carry hoop loads.
- o A metal shield design which consists of a metal shell and a graphite/"epoxy" core. This design would look like a conventional retaining ring and would use normal attachment techniques.

A fourth design, which was similar to the combination hydraulic press fit with bonded joint, except that a key arrangement was substituted for the bonded joint, was also considered. It was assumed that with additional development work these four designs would meet all the retaining ring requirements. In order to choose the best alternative, these four designs (along with the conventional steel retaining ring design) were compared using a Design Matrix Analysis. A total of 29 Wants and seven Possible Consequences were considered. The "scores" are listed below:

	<u>Wants</u>	<u>Consequences</u>
Conventional RR	1,900	-5
Metal Shield	1,900	0
Combination Hydraulic/Bond	1,400	-4
Hydraulic With Keys	1,300	-7
Active Damper Ring	1,000	-15

On a "Wants" basis, the metal shield design gave the same "score" as the conventional steel retaining ring and was far superior to the other two alternatives.

The conventional steel retaining ring showed very low risks (the negative consequences had low probabilities); however, the present steel ring may not be suitable for advanced designs - the positive consequences also have low probabilities. The metal shield design looks very promising even though there are some high risks associated with this design. The Active Damper Ring concept appears quite risky.

The metal shield design is clearly the best graphite/epoxy composite retaining ring design but is in the early stages of development.

CONCLUSIONS

The combined results of this study, from design to spin testing, have demonstrated the feasibility of using bias ply wound graphite/epoxy composite retaining rings to replace metallic retaining rings. However, significant problems which center around attachment and negative sequence current flow remain to be solved. One difficulty is that there is no proven technique for attaching graphite epoxy retaining rings.

Spin testing has shown that there is more than sufficient hoop strength in graphite/epoxy rings; therefore, it may be more advantageous to optimize the

laminare construction based on deflection rather than strength. This would allow the designer more options in developing a suitable attachment scheme.

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